

SELF-STUDY DIFFERENCES OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES BETWEEN LOCAL AND INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The article will study the quality of knowledge of foreign languages of local and foreign students, what scientific research was conducted and came to conclusions on how to increase the effectiveness of independent learning. Theses and recommendations in the field of self-education in Uzbekistan will also be considered.

Keywords: *foreign languages, self-study, high education, skills, understanding, essence, technique, improvement, practice, method, interactive, Independent work of students, autonomous learning, creative tasks, authentic texts, terminological vocabulary, intercultural.*

The changes taking place in the life of society, caused by the process of globalization, could not but affect education. Currently, higher education is undergoing a process of reform and the emergence of new pedagogical paradigms, shifting emphasis from educational activities to self-educational ones. The acquisition of knowledge, skills and professional qualities is facilitated by independent work, which is a transitional step between teaching and self-education. Even in the transitional period of higher education in Uzbekistan, today foreign experience is being studied with great attention to self-study. Since 2019, educational reforms have been carried out at the Tashkent State University of Law, the ground has been created for self-study of students. Nevertheless, the introduction of independent learning and its effective use in the institutions of teaching and learning foreign languages, which is difficult to imagine without the intervention of a teacher, requires a lot of experience. The challenges of the 21st century dictate that a higher education graduate must be prepared for independent professional and educational activities, respond to newly emerging professional challenges, be able to find the rational in a large flow of information, work with related industries, etc [1]. In addition, a modern professional should be able to work in temporary project teams, to professionally discuss and solve complex problems and tasks. In the new educational paradigm, the

student must turn from a passive consumer of knowledge into an active subject. In this perspective, independent work of students becomes not just an important form of the educational process, it turns into its basis.

On May 6 this year, under the chairmanship of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev, a videoconference was held on measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages. In our country, several areas of science are selected and developed with special attention every year. This year, physics and foreign languages have been identified as such priority areas. The policy of openness of Uzbekistan, its active entry into the world market, the expansion of international cooperation in all areas increase the need for knowledge of foreign languages. Today, education is conducted in foreign languages in 25 higher educational institutions of our country. In 2016 there were only 7 of them. The number of graduates who have received an international language certificate has increased 10 times over the past 3 years [2].

Uzbekistan is ranked 88 out of 112 in the EF English Proficiency Index (EF EPI) 2021 global English proficiency ranking. The rating is based on the results of testing 2 million adults in countries and regions of the world for which English is not their first language [3].

The main goals of self-study of students in Uzbekistan are:

- the acquisition of new methods of obtaining knowledge, the ability to independently analyze processes;
- consolidation, deepening, expansion and systematization of knowledge gained in the classroom;
- training in working with legal acts, information and special literature;
- independent study of educational materials;
- development of activity, acquisition of knowledge, creative initiative, responsibility and order;
- formation of the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in practice;
- independent thinking, self-development, formation of the implementation of one's own plan;
- develop the ability to research.

The main task of independent learning of students is to develop the acquisition of knowledge by the method of independent search for information, the formation of an active interest in a creative approach to the educational process. Students must independently form their own independent opinion and conclusions based on a deep

analysis of the problems posed in the preparation of the term paper, course project, final qualifying work and master's theses! [4]

The concept of 40% theory and 60% practice was developed in higher education. According to him, students mostly use the professor as a mentor and do their own research. However, it should be noted the lack of information in the Uzbek language in order to better learn a foreign language and show high-level results. The conditions for access and use of some sources of information are created only for undergraduates and doctoral students. In addition, despite the fact that students are given the opportunity to independently study, they still do not have the freedom to choose a scientific direction and topic.

According to the information provided by the department of assessment of knowledge and proficiency in foreign languages of the State Testing Center, 11,250 out of 1,066,926 applicants enrolled in undergraduate programs of higher educational institutions at the beginning of the 2019/20 academic year have a foreign language diploma. The main part of these certificates is the national CEFR certificate issued on the basis of the IELTS and DTM exams. In addition to English, the DTM has a national certification system based on an exam in 13 other languages. Compared to the previous year (2018), in the 2019/20 academic year, for areas of study in which a foreign language is the first subject, a foreign language proficiency certificate issued by the DTM (national certificate) or IELTS (5.5), TOEFL IBT (72 points) language proficiency level V2 and higher according to international testing systems is required. For areas of education where a foreign language is not the main subject, 4.5 points are requested in the IELTS exam, 42 points in TOEFL IBT, V1 and above in the SEFR exam. [5] Furthermore, this year, IELTS level B2 language certificate is required for admission to the master's program, along with other official documents. In our opinion, this also serves as a motivation for local students to study a foreign language on their own.

Foreign universities in the United States and Europe believe that the necessary requirement for the successful organization and implementation of the SIW in a foreign language is the control of independent tasks performed by students, assessment of the progress and content of independent work, its results, as well as the formation of students' skills of self-control and self-esteem, Z.T. Voroshnina. For this purpose, educational and methodological materials developed and adapted to the needs of students are used, consisting of methodological recommendations for planning and organizing independent work, exemplary samples of completed tests,

business correspondence templates, reference dictionaries, a set of special original texts and assignments for them, links to useful websites and relevant literature. [6]

One of the factors for optimizing the SIW in order to improve the quality of language education is the computerization of the process of learning a foreign language, which provides everyone with access to educational sites, electronic dictionaries and textbooks, educational methodological complexes, and a variety of interactive programs. With the help of Internet resources, students can submit completed lexical and grammatical exercises for verification in real time, get advice from a teacher on the effective assimilation of educational material, conduct an interactive exchange of views with their comrades on the joint performance of creative tasks in projects, complete a test, translate in writing a piece of special text or write a business document. Such tasks allow foreign students to show their creativity and originality of thinking, to form a constant need to improve their language and special knowledge. On the other hand, an individual approach to each student is carried out, their level of preparation, personal interests and inclinations are taken into account.

In particular, you can see the ranking of how well European students know English:

№	Country	EF Index
1	Netherlands	652
2	Denmark	632
3	Finland	631
4	Sweden	625
5	Norway	624[7]

In European conditions, the role of a foreign language teacher is changing and even becoming more complicated, who must be well versed in modern telecommunication technologies, monitor the emergence of new Internet resources in order to be able to act as an organizer, moderator, partner and adviser to students in matters of independent study of a foreign language. It is the teacher, according to A.V.Vayakhin and M.V.Kravchenko, is a coordinator who interacts with classroom and independent work of students, a consultant who provides differentiated and

individual assistance in language education, a mentor and a source of fresh ideas in the implementation of student projects of a creative nature.

In the era of globalization, in order to implement the concept of intercultural language education (N.V. Baryshnikov, N.D. Galskova, I.A. Orekhova, E.I. Passov, V.V. Safonova, P.V. Sysoev and others) when teaching a foreign language to future specialists in the field of international economic relations, it is also necessary to emphasize the special role of the organization SIW, highlight its features in the context of the formation of socio-cultural competence [8].

Conclusion:

It is necessary that the student knows the teaching aids and knows how to use them: he orients himself in the textbook, knows what, where and how is located in the textbook, knows how to use magnetic recording, a dictionary, a grammar guide, and understands the purpose for which certain exercises, tasks are performed. [9]

Independent work solves a very important task - a more perfect, linguistically competent functioning of the language, conscious assimilation of the rules for the formation and normative use of the language. And this generally improves communicative communication in one form or another of communicative activity. Solving the problem of independent work can provide effective conditions for improving the quality of teaching a foreign language, give the theoretical content an applied character, and also constitute an important prerequisite for further self-education.

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